

Case Report

A Case Report on Mayer Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser (Mrkh) Syndrome

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ABSTRACT

Mayer Rokitansky Kuster Hauser syndrome (MRKHS) is a congenital malformation of female genital tract. In MRKHS there is uterine agenesis or hypoplasia of proximal vagina due to interrupted embryonic development of para-mesonephric ducts. We report a case of type 2 MRKHS with left crossed fused renal ectopia. Ultrasonography findings were absent uterus, normal bilateral ovaries, left crossed fused ectopia with left dilated tortuous ureter which was confirmed on MRI. For management and corrective of surgery of patient correct diagnosis is essential.

INTRODUCTION

Mayer-Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser Syndrome (MRKHS) or Mullerian dysgenesis is an infrequent congenital syndrome. Incidence of MRKHS is 1 in 5000 females. It is characterized by uterine agenesis or hypoplasia of proximal vagina due to interrupted embryonic development of para-mesonephric ducts with normal karyotype 46XX and normal secondary sexual characteristics¹. They are of two types: type 1 having only uterovaginal agenesis and type 2 having uterovaginal agenesis with anomalies in fallopian tube, kidney, spine, heart and other organ and amenorrhea with painful sexual intercourse¹. For normal married life counseling of the patient and surgical correction by neo vagina creation for sexual intercourse is the treatment of choice. Here, we report a case of type 2 MRKHS with left crossed fused renal ectopia as per SCARE 2020 criteria². The MRKH syndrome had a significant influence on both fertility and psychological health of women, therefore correct diagnosis with accurate anatomical details is required for counseling of the patient and management by surgical correction.

CASE REPORT

A 21 year old unmarried girl presented to our hospital with the chief complaints of primary amenorrhea. She had normal secondary sexual characteristics. There was no family history of primary amenorrhea. There was no history of antenatal exposure to her mother for any medication. Patient had no past medical or surgical history.

Trans-abdominal ultrasound scanning of patient showed absent uterus, normal bilateral ovaries showing non-dominant follicles, left crossed fused ectopia and dilated and tortuous left ureter. MRI on T2W image showed dilated tortuous ureter with left cross fused renal ectopia and blind ended vagina with normal bilateral ovaries.

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Figure-1: USG grey scale images showing A - Absent uterus with blind ended vagina B- Dilated tortuous left ureter C - Normal left ovary D- Normal right ovary E - Left cross fused renal ectopia

[C]

[D]

[E]

Figure-2: MR T2W images showing A - Left dilated tortuous ureter B - left cross fused renal ectopia C- blind ended vagina D - Normal left ovary E – Normal right ovary

DISCUSSION

Mayer-Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser syndrome (mullerian agenesis) is a spectrum of congenital anomalies with no known exact cause however mutation in WNT4 gene may be the cause of Mullerian aplasia³. In MRKHS, patient has varying spectrum of utero-vaginal agenesis with normal ovaries and normal secondary sexual characteristics¹. Uterus and proximal vagina may be absent or rudimentary as bilateral and non-cannulated muscular buds. Patient has bilateral normal ovaries and fallopian tubes with normal endocrine and cytogenetic evaluations⁴. This case presented with mullerian agenesis and left crossed fused renal ectopia which is classified as MRKHS type 2 association. MRKHS type 2 may be rarely associated with anomalies of upper urinary tract, skeletal and cardiac defects¹.

Urinary tract malformations are seen in 40% of the cases which mainly includes unilateral renal agenesis, hypoplastic kidneys, horse shoe shaped kidneys and hydronephrosis¹. Skeletal anomalies are seen in 30–40% of the cases¹. It includes scoliosis, isolated vertebral anomalies, ribs malformations, and spina bifida. Involvement of face and limbs is rarely seen¹. Limb

[A]

[B]

abnormality includes ectrodactyly, duplicated thumb¹. Auditory defects are seen in 25% of MHRC type 2 cases with conductive deafness due to stapedial ankylosis due to middle ear malformations or sensorineural defects of varying severity¹. Cardiac malformations may be tetralogy of fallot, atrial septal defect and conotruncal defects like pulmonary valvular stenosis¹. The diagnosis of MRKH mainly depends on imaging study. Transabdominal ultrasonography is the first line investigation but abdomino-pelvic MRI gives more precise and clear information than the sonography⁵.

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